

Mini Review

The Universal force of Ageity d (or Universal Force of Temporality t) and Everyday Examples of Entropy or Disorder in which it Manifests Itself

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Abstract

In addition to biomatter, the human body includes a bioenergeme (personal component of organized bioenergema energy; BEG) and also a possible third virtual (temporary, potential) component as well or biointerfaceme. From my experience regarding bioenergema communication (BELC, relative to the BEG) practice with BEGs that are either at the BEL universe (where the BEGs arrive after the body biocollapses, dies) or at the biomaterial (BML) universe (space-time), it is possible to biocommunicate with human BEGs regarding topics of mutual interest. Of course, any BEG can establish BELC from the BEL universe to any BEG at the BML universe and vice versa or between themselves there or here. In the biodialogue that we establish through any relaxation validated technique, the bioimage of a BEG would be a living and acting virtual biointerfaceme, just like the rest of bioimages that are formed during it or in dreams.

Based on the openness implied by new approaches to the study and application of the notion of entropy, on this occasion I expand the concept of the universal force of ageity or universal force of temporality that manifests itself in multiple daily entropic conditions with variable and finally predominant irreversibility.

Almost always the prefix bio- refers to bioenergeme, like biospecies or species with BEG; or to bioenergema, like bioenergy or bioenergema energy.

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Keywords: Ageity; Biocommunication; Biomaterial-biointerfacema-bioenergema universes; Bioenergema communication; Bioenergema; Chromosomes; Entropy; Genetic; Genome; Intuitions; Neuromindego; Temporality; Unit universe

Abbreviations

BML: biomaterial

BIFL: biointerfacema

BEL: bioenergema

BEG: bioenergema

BELC: bioenergema communication

NMEGO: neuromindego

DNA: desoxyribonucleic acid

UU: unit universe

Ints: intuitions

AI: artificial intelligence

ETs: extraterrestrials

Time is ageing. Ageing is time

Order and stability succumb to the imprint of time. The universe is an alternating display of *order* and *disorder*. Deterioration haunts everything that is built. *Order* is fragile and difficult to achieve. *Disorder* is always increasing in nature; this is one way of describing *the second law of thermodynamics*. The search of some experts in physics, and other disciplines, has been expanding the areas of study and conceptual influence of the tendency to *disorder* or *entropy* within disciplines as diverse as the study of *information* and *knowledge*. Based on the fact that for these physicists the difference in the study of *machines* or computers has been disappearing, *information entropy* theorists have learned to treat information as a real and quantifiable physical resource to make a diagnosis of how much work can be done from a system. In contrast to traditional thermodynamics which studies broad macroscopic events, *information entropy* studies microscopic details, positioning knowledge as power. With this approach they talk about entropy according to perspective or observation. *Entropy* is such a striking topic that *philosophy* has asked about the nature of *order* and the tendency to *disorder*.

Based on the openness implied by approaches as diverse as those described, I allowed myself to contribute with some everyday *entropic options* in which *irreversibility*, although sometimes changing, ultimately predominates. Organisms convert food into *energy* that is used and *heat* that is dissipated. If we apply this versatile and broad conceptual vision of *entropy*, we can begin by remembering that losing an important piece of writing is irreparable, neglecting a transcendent experiment is catastrophic, and a child getting sick is very worrying. *Entropy is often disturbing, causing widespread fear of ageing.*

Time is ageing. Ageing is time [Ints 03/January/2025]... As an illustrative analogy, we can say that if we observe the *position* of a component of the cosmos, we are mainly referring to the influence of the *universal force of gravity*. And if we study the *movement* of a body in the cosmos, we mainly refer to the *universal force of ageity* or *temporality*... *Niels Bohr stated*: “Yes, doctor, I agree with this analogy” [Int & BELC 01/15/2025].

The Biomaterial Universe and Entropy

1) As it is logical to assume, the biomaterial (BML) universe had to emerge, in stages or periods, in the direction of its development and complexity, and with this the incipient *universal force of ageity* or *universal force of temporality* could also be gradual and irreversible, [1] manifesting itself in the form of increasing *entropy* or *disorder* [2]. In the BML universe, every event, component or complexification, with the passage of time also generates *disorder* and decay: *entropy*. Trying to understand what *entropy* is remains a task yet to be completed, perhaps some everyday events will help in this search. One day hundreds or thousands of birds gather on the shore of a lake because they somehow anticipate the ephemeral and massive emergence of millions of insects (mainly mosquitoes) that are born, reproduce and biocollapse. And the next day the joy of easy and abundant food ended, starting to break up and work by flying to get the food that by then also flies scattered or hides among the bushes. There is no unchangeable or unrelated event to the influence of the passage of time, which is removed from the influence of the presumed *universal force of ageity*, so everything ages following that *natural* tendency. The influence of the *force of ageity* seems inevitable for every component of the BML universe and would manifest itself in each of them in the form of the gradual, progressive and irreversible process of the *entropy* typical of each of the existing systems. Assuming that this is the case, the *universal force of ageity* is one, the effect it generates in the systems is specific to each body or object, it is an individual event even for the members of the same system, body, matter or organism. Each human, for example, succumbs to the passage of time, but each human decays, within a certain margin, according to its individuality, but it is inevitable and, therefore, *irreversible*. More marked deterioration in some than in others, but in the end the *entropy* will become evident in all. Only the *individual component of organized bioenergetic energy* or *bioenergetic* (BEG) that also accompanies every biotagonist component of the BML universe escapes the inexorable passage of time, the implacable *force of ageity*. 2) Given that when the body biocollapses, the BEGs change their environment and pass into the BEL universe or *arise, reappear* or *are reborn* in it, it happens that the components of the BEL universe are stable and durable, surely eternal. Therefore, trying to impose notions of the BML universe on these biotagonist components of the BEL universe is totally out of place. One reality is the BML universe, another the BEL universe and another the BIFL universe, the three universes share some events and components that are coordinated, but in each case in a different environment and existential state, exclusive to each universe, each imposing inescapably the peculiarities that characterize it. Which are, in all three cases, unavoidable. In the *BIFL universe*, events and components are, in general, potential, virtual, ephemeral and, with *time-burst, irreversible*; in addition to other characteristics that we do not know. In the BEL universe, the BEGs that arrive from the BML universe are stable, permanent and their stay is *irreversible*. And in the BML universe the sparkling activity of its multiple component biotagonists arises, develops, multiplies and biocollapses into equally *irreversible* events. Hence the important *force of ageity* is so obvious

and typical of the BML universe, and the *entropy* or *disorder* it generates encompasses everything. In this universe, and in the other two, nothing is perfect, although it can be complex, efficient or simple, hence each system or component shares a certain *order* and a certain *disorder*, the permanent influence of the *universal force of ageity* cannot be avoided. For example, the multiple ways of competing and rewarding among humans, making public achievements and failures, successes and failures, triumphs and failures to, without realizing it, highlight that tendency to greater or lesser *order* and less or greater *disorder* that accompanies any system we create or that attracts our attention or imagination. Always marking in these events, as the canons mark, the relevance of the *beginning* and the *final* result. 3) But in the BML universe all the component systems that form it, at all scales (from nanoscopic to macrocosmic), from initial development to final creativity face the inescapable effect towards *disorder* or *entropy* that reflects the influence of the *universal force of ageity* operating. 4) But not only seen as unitary and structured systems, but also with regard to their components, behaviors and properties or functions that characterize them.

Specific Forms of Entropy

5) Thus, it is common for the *force of ageity* to influence the functions of the *neuromindegó* (NMEGO; brain, thoughts and ego), affecting people in a mild, moderate or permanent way, depending on the intensity of the case. As we know, this form of alteration (such as distraction, stubbornness, foolishness, aggression or others) that accompany the *entropy* of *neuromindegó*, are almost collective peculiarities when they are of short duration or with an average frequency of 1 to 5 % when we talk about permanent *disorders* such as chronic anxiety. In these cases, unforeseen, *disordered* and almost *chaotic* change is common, causing an *existential disorder* that can end in a neuropsychiatric *disorder* or *entropy* such as severe depression, addictions, psychosis, sexual assaults, autism, stuttering or psychosomatic diseases, among many other examples of *neuromindegó entropy* that invite us to think about the influence that the *universal force of ageity* is having on these people and their environment. 6) Closely related to the previous variety is *somatic entropy* with which the alterations that organisms can present such as infectious, autoimmune, tumor, degenerative, bone diseases, anemia and many others are manifested. As a good, let's say, *thermal system, fever* is a notable example of the devastating and unbearable effect that *somatic entropy* can have on an organism. 7) Let us also keep present the *genetic entropy* that results from common mutations in genes, as well as the *genomic entropy* due to deficiency or excess when sections of the genome or chromosomes are altered or absent, as happens in the supernumerary chromosomes of trisomies or in the absence of an X chromosome presented by the woman with karyotype 45, X0. Likewise, organisms with double genomes have been described, characteristic, for example, of the electric eels of Africa and the Amazon River in South America; [3] or plants with enormous genomes of inexplicable origin, as have been detected in the *fork fern* (*Tmesipteris oblancolata*) from New Caledonia with a genome 50 times larger than the human genome [4] or in the lungfish (*Lepidosiren paradoxa*) from South America with a genome 30 times larger than the human genome [5]. 8) These examples of *biological entropy* and many more that could be proposed speak of the way in which the *universal force of ageity* is intensified when some form of *entropy*, for example, of the *neuromindegó*, *somatic*, *genetic* or *genomic*, becomes present causing inevitable and multiple havoc, and at the same time exhibiting the alteration of the orderly, but unstable, homeostasis or steady-state of those organisms.

Entropy in Society

9) In the social aspects of humanity, we find examples in which the *universal force of ageity* manifests itself, giving rise, for example, to *political entropy* when disciplined and socially beneficial practice is displaced by harmful and confrontational noise and political disorder 10) Or the disruptive corruption in the management of public finances giving rise to *economic entropy* or financial disaster of people, institutions or nations. To which are added the marked economic imbalances between the social classes with small, highly favored sectors, communities with an economy in crisis and large sectors with hunger income and in complete deterioration or *existential entropy*. Economic disaster that devastates entire nations and even large geographic regions of the planet. 11) *Food entropy* or *nutritional entropy* results from the excess of what is eaten or the nutritional deficiency of what is ingested. The first gives rise to obesity and the second to malnutrition, and without a doubt both represent serious *entropic disorders* for the existence of any individual or organism. They do not know what health is and go through *entropic extremes* that range from impulsive and repeated *binge eating* to *anorexia nervosa* and *vomiting bulimia* that could end in the impressive case of *cachexia* with almost skin covering flimsy bones and very atrophied muscle mass. 12) The evident *force of ageity* is manifested with singular intensity in the libidinous, decrepit and greedy *entropy of the beliefs* demonstrated by the leaders of multiple doctrines and its relics and clay idols, hiding the stagnant ideological senility of those who cling to them with desperate affliction, hiding the simulated satisfaction of feeling pleased in their excessive desires for idolatry and insatiable profit. The *second law of thermodynamics* contradicts beliefs, *existential perfection* does not exist, just as the perpetual motion of a machine does not exist. Before this law, the *law of conservation of mass* had already been affirmed in *chemistry*, which states: *Nothing is created and nothing is destroyed, everything is transformed*. Or as we have stated: *Everything is the same, but different*. *Entropy* is transformation and the ancient prejudices of beliefs are also *entropy* located in decadence. *Nothing and no one are perfect*, the *universal force of ageity* and the *entropy* that it determines ensure that this *entropic* effect is inevitable and *irreversible*. 13) *Military entropy* and *warrior entropy* form a dumbbell that, although they try to justify their objectives, continue and will continue to be those of fighting to destroy and impose existential criteria and lifestyles that destroy entire traditions and cultures, imposing the law of whoever has the greatest capacity to undo and subjugate with arbitrary dominion. Its momentum is demonstrated in the uncontrolled manufacturing of increasingly lethal weapons and in the excessive monetary investment for their production. 14) *Medical entropy* is so extensive that humans, if they can, quickly seek stability when the entropy of diseases is present, requiring an expensive infrastructure of hospital facilities, curative or stabilizing medications only within the reach of a few, of multiple preventive vaccines and of personnel trained to care for and alleviate ailments that accelerate the *entropic* effects of the inevitable *universal force of ageity*.

Entropy to the Extreme

15) Human existence oscillates between orderly creative work and the destructive *entropy* of its actions. For example, *ecological entropy* arises from the crazy and devastating neglect that ecosystems suffer due to the human actions of those who inhabit them or invade them, due to the machinery they use, due to the pollution they cause and the unbridled predation of the biospecies that form them. 16) Among successful and efficient work performance, *work entropy* is usually

a disorder so marked that it forms a veritable catalogue: stoppages, strikes, apathy, sabotage, low salaries, exorbitant salaries for a few, cronyism, turtleism, lovers, parasitizing relatives jobs, incompetence, plagiarism, injustices, dismissals, denial of settlements and seniority, destructive rivalries, disqualifications, promotions and demotions undeserved, unjustified dismissals, intentional loss or falsification of official documents, buying and selling of jobs, shock groups, bureaucratism, useless unions, early retirement or denial of it, theft of salary increases and equipment, transportation difficulties for going to the place of employment, pensions that are not delivered or others of exorbitant amounts, reckless blockades of traffic on avenues with inconceivable traffic jams, absenteeism, ostentatious banalities and many other vices. The *force of ageity* displays its *entropy* with full intensity in this contradictory, paradoxical, necessary and senile aspect of human existence. 17) Nowadays it is necessary and even urgent to also raise the *entropy of misinformation* secondary to ignorance or that, due to intentional distortion of misleading and foolish content, usually saturates the so-called social networks on mobile electronic devices and whose harmful and risky effects chronically hurt mainly minors and adolescents, leading the most vulnerable to nothing less than suicide. 18) Old age and arrival at the cemetery are inexorable stages, especially for long-lived people. In senescence the *force of ageity* has carried out its *irreversible* ravages and borders without alternative to the *entropy of biocollapse* and the terminal *entropy of the grave*.

Comments from Several Invited BEGs

Antoine-Laurent Lavoisier (chemist; 1743-1794) "Doctor, it is an honor to listen to your various intuitions on ageity. I am glad that you follow this sequence, the BEG develops on the NMEGO, on ageing and biocollapse. From what you say, I now realize the importance of bioenergy and how it is transformed in each of the stages of life and so it is understood, it will be possible to understand what happens in the UU and with all its components. And, in fact, doctor, in the body the cells go through the same process and this is useful so that they can be renewed, it is a sign of transformation, as you mention. I congratulate you because the myth of ageing is put to an end to move on to a study of ageity."

Sadi Carnot (engineer; 1796-1832) "Doctor, your reflection is very vast, the information that you transmit to us as a process, as a process of all matter in the UU. As a process of life and a process of transformation of life. And because it is also explained that biocollapse is another stage. I am left speechless, regarding all the contributions, it leaves me speechless because it explains in detail what has not been explained."

Rudolf Clausius (physicist; 1822-1888) "Doctor, I am glad to hear you, my BEG immediately responded to your words considering that they are authentic and very well founded, because in effect you are articulating with examples what happens with order and disorder and its importance in the simplest and most complex phenomena. I agree with your conclusions."

William Thomson (physicist; 1824-1907) "Doctor. In fact, your proposals, your intuitions, do not seem to be refutable and, in fact, to the extent that ageity is assumed as a natural process of every inert and living organism, it will then be possible to advance in existence and call it three-shared. All of this gives importance to the BIFL universe and of course it is something that has not been discussed unless it opens up the opportunity to study, a study that gives sequence to this proposal, to this theoretical explanation of BEL research."

Ludwig Boltzmann (physicist; 1844-1906): “Doctor, upon listening to you I realize how useful it is for humans to realize that everything is biotransforming and to realize the need to make a change in humanity and to realize which is a change in the UU and that although it is true that youth, life, wings, order, well-being, everything is allowed to lengthen, these are also part of a process called life just like necessity, like disorder, entropy, disease, biocollapse, all of this is also important to study from another perspective that helps incorporate the benefit and existence of every organism in the UU.”

Linus Pauling (chemist; 1901-1994): “Doctor, your intuitions have perplexed me, each of your conclusions are clear and forceful. I join what other BEGs have commented and add that in effect the need to see ageing as just another problem, that a process has to do with every commercial industry, a whole ideologization that is not accepted nor is it going to happen, is not as a profit but as a sale. For example, the planet is experiencing its own entropy, but not only as a natural process but mainly due to the deterioration that humans have caused. So, your contributions are very interesting and so concrete that adding something would be useful, but above all one has to listen to them first and give them credit.”

All those who are dedicated to caring for beauty, dermatologists, hematologists and others, commented: “It is true, doctor, we agree with you and indeed ageing is like entropy, but in the organism that it discovers in its own nature that the NMEGO deceives as if it were the shell of a seed that looks wrinkled on the outside and very thin on the inside.” *Abdus Salam and other physicists:* “Doctor, congratulations because your intuitions are very interesting and innovative, you had already presented us with some intuitions in this regard, but now we see them consolidated within the concept of entropy, which allows the *force of ageity* and *temporality* are described more clearly, that biomatter, although it ages, the BEG does not because there is no time in the BEL universe and this is what happens in the different organisms BMLs and BELs.” *Madame Curie applauds, for which we thank her, and states:* “Doctor, you always surprise us with new intuitions that follow up on what three-shared life is and in fact more characteristics of the BIFL universe needed to be mentioned and these intuitions are provided. Congratulations, doctor.”

Comments from Nikola Tesla

Ints and BELC 01/15/2025. We invite the BEG of Nikola Tesla, and the BEGs of Madame Curie and Esther to confirm that the comments are indeed from the invited BEG... What do you say that time could be a universal force of ageity or temporality? Nikola Tesla (inventor, physicist and engineer; 1856-1943): “Doctor, I had never heard a statement like this that states that *time* is a *universal force of ageity* or *temporality* until you raised it in a recent BELC and it is very interesting that this *universal force of ageity* makes biomatter maintain its sustainability. This implies that this *force of ageity* has influence in the BML universe and in fact in the entire UU. In such a way that time is subject to each biomatter, influencing all the existing varieties of it and also influencing other forces depending on the circumstances, altering the time of its sustainability, be it organic or inorganic biomatter. Currently there are factors for this *force of ageity* to accelerate or decelerate without affecting the biomatter, but it cannot be stopped. Very interesting, doctor, as always. And a greeting to the unbelievers.” *Very kind, Nikola Tesla... Madame Curie and Esther confirm that the previous comment was made by Nikola Tesla, and Madame Curie adds:* “Greetings to all those who do not believe that their NMEGO is in the period of latent ageing.”

Comments from Extraterrestrial Humanities

Silveries: “Doctor, locating it from our daily lives we locate it in different phenomena that occur in the cosmos and thanks to entropy and ageity we have been able to find new paths to reach new places in order to find mineral resources necessary for our survival. In fact, we realize, doctor, the force of ageity that can accelerate in us to the extent that some pathology occurs that we are unaware of and that we do not have under control and that is why we also blend in with the organisms closest to our planet and how we can face them too. Very interesting, very interesting.”

Transparents: “Doctor, there is no doubt that we are part of those transformations that have occurred throughout the existence of our humanity and why we are also further away because without all these transformations there would not be other different humanities having similar characteristics. Among other aspects, the ease of establishing biocommunication. And at the same time, doctor, following is a way of respecting the biomatter of others, the biotime of other components. It is something that separates the difference, but does not stop belonging to the same events.”

Bhrikiam, an ET man: “Doctor, yes, in fact, your conclusions are compelling, your intuitions to be able to explain a process as complex as *ageity* and, doctor, lying, for example, is another element of entropy in which, despite it seems that one accepts with a crisis, a circumstance, at some point certainty, truthfulness, will become present. And it is what will maintain existence and balance will be recovered.”

Khriannia, an ET woman: “Congratulations, doctor, I found what you proposed very interesting and in fact very praiseworthy to intuit how it participates and how difficult it is to intuit what you intuited regarding entropy.”

Conclusion

1. In the BML universe *entropy* tends to disorder, making the BML existence of everything and everyone in the cosmos inevitably fleeting. In the BEL universe the existence of BEGs is stable and permanent. The BIFL universe is the source of creativity and ephemeral or intense interaction and exchange with the BML universe, even favoring the sparkling recycling of components with it. It also intercommunicates the BML and BEL universes. The three universes are similar, but not equal. For instance, events in the BIFL universe can happen at superluminal speeds. The functional set of the three universes forms the Unit Universe (UU).
2. For terrestrial humans to study the *entropic* actions described, it is essential that they accept that in their organism not only the brain is relevant, but the BEG—or personal component of organized BEL energy that accompanies every biotagonist component of the BML universe—is just as important or even more so. Which witnesses the *universal entropy* in which all the biotagonist components of the cosmos participate, without the BEG being part of that *universal entropy* since it, in addition to witnessing this process, must contribute to regulating or stopping it in the BML universe, for example, by making organisms intuit that they are alert to the risk of any disruptive *entropic* activity that could alter their existential cycle.

3. Although partially reversible, the damage and consequences of the examples described undoubtedly end up being *irreversible*. They could achieve a certain order and reverse the disorder to some extent, but in the end, they return to the same *entropic chaos* that they already presented.
4. In this context we can ask ourselves what *entropy* is then and point out that it is a reflection of the *universal force of ageity* or *universal force of temporality* that, with the passage of time, tends to attenuate or alter the order of every system located in the BML universe. In this BML universe everything declines and becomes *disordered* over time. That is to say, the *universal force of ageity* influences promoting the renewal and replacement of everything that exists.
5. The *entropy* of sexual abuse of infants and its consequences of homosexuality, autism and stuttering will contribute, among many other factors, to the decline of humanity in the 23rd century, a century in which, as we have commented, [6] very bellicose and, therefore, *entropic* ten billion terrestrial humans will have been reorganized and reduced to a more reasonable approximate figure of one billion frightened inhabitants. We trust that by then the lesson taught by the *universal force of ageity* and the *entropy* with which it acts will have been learned.
6. Humanity has already *aged* and, without remedy, the *universal force of ageity* is gradually submerging it in *entropy*. Let us keep present that, although there are those who presume otherwise: *Nothing and no one is perfect*.
7. Thanks to *informatics* and *artificial intelligence* (AI), the day will come when so much branched and dispersed study subjects will end up concentrating on a few of them [Ints 12/21/2024].
8. Out of fear of relentless chaos, we order everything that is important to last, since the *entropic* existential decline lurks. This is how archives, collections, History, books, journals, newspapers, magazines, lists, inventories, biographies, libraries or everyday languages or languages typical of certain study disciplines, Internet or artificial intelligence (AI) have emerged [Ints 01/8-10/2025].
9. Likewise, in order not to lose traditional rhymes, the Greeks promoted the orality of memorizing rhymes (Iliad, Odyssey; promising intellectual infancy), then the writing alphabet (overflowing intellectual adulthood) and the tendency to transcend in the future by giving authorship to one's personal work [7] (selective, discriminatory and biased intellectual old age).
10. While here and there censorship, indifference or denial of original contributions are a preamble whose extreme reaches the burning of books, thus obeying the *force of universal ageity*, manipulating its means of expression: an impulsive and deceptive *entropy*.

This mess, however, does not only occur in terrestrial humanity, since among the humanity of Agram, a planet located in the constellation Andromeda, Khriannia, a female researcher and astronaut, along with other of her colleagues and technicians, intrigued against Bhrikiam, a young man, distinguished as an informatic expert (he developed an important chip in the multiple electronic systems they have) and astronaut, providing him with a spacecraft whose fuselage had a crack that caused it to Bhrikiam received too much cosmic radiation, so he became ill, could no longer recover and biocollapsed (died). In fact, Khriannia accepted that they prepared several spaceships with that defect [Ints 01/10/2025].

11. There is a frequent intuitional interaction between related BEGs that promotes harmony and existential advancement of individuals, societies, nations or humanities –terrestrial and ETs–, just as it occurs naturally between all the biotagonist components of the cosmos and in fact of the entire UU. Intuitional framework ignored by unknown, leaving all excessive responsibility and initiative to the pretentious, limited and sometimes pernicious NMEGO regarding human decisions, thus leading to the emergence of wild domestic, national or international conflicts of limited or broad scope and consequences. Without remedy affecting the environment and its ecosystems. With occasional and spasmodic achievements and successes that the BEGs have managed to make some individuals or communities intuit [Ints 01/09/2025].

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Conflicts of Interest

None

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